

Day 1. Wednesday, October 8 2025

14:00 - 18:00 CEST, online

14:00 - 14:20	About eDNAqua-Plan Nicolas Page (EMBRC) What do we want to achieve with this workshop? Katrina Exter (VLIZ)
14:20 - 14:50	Mapping the eDNA data ecosystem: the Landscaping report Emilie Boulanger (UNESCO)
14:50 - 15:20	Plenary discussion time Your first thoughts on the current and future maps and the recommendations
15:20 - 15:35 15:35 - 15:45	Break Introduction to our Miro boards These will be used during the breakout sessions. Followed by a short break
15:45 - 16:30	Breakout session 1 Random assignment of attendees into three groups to each discuss different questions on the landscape and its recommendations and requirements
16:30 - 16:45 16:45 - 16:55	5 min summary of each breakout A summary of what each breakout has discussed Break
16:55 - 17:40	Breakout session 2 Random assignment again of attendees into three groups to each discuss different questions on the landscape and its recommendations and requirements
17:40 - 18:00	5 min summary of each breakout Summary of Day 1 and explanation of Day 2

Day 2. Thursday, 9 October 2025

14:00 - 18:00 CEST, online

14:00 - 14:30	A recap of day 1 and outline of day 2 Katrina Exter (VLIZ) How to use the Miro boards today Emilie Boulanger (UNESCO)
14:30 - 15:30	Breakout Sessions A Data publishers (DNA and biodiversity) Katrina Exter (VLIZ) and Christina Pavludi (EMBRC) B Reference libraries, Bioinformatics, Taxonomies (data) Emilie Boulanger and Saara Suominen (UNESCO) C Biobanks, Culture collections, Taxonomies (concepts) Pascal Hablutzel (VLIZ) and Tom Collart (Seascope Belgium) Attendees can select their own groups Attendees can take breaks as and when they wish during the session
15:30 - 16:00	Plenary: summary of the breakouts / Break
16:00 - 17:00	Breakout Sessions A Data publishers (DNA and biodiversity) Katrina Exter (VLIZ) and Christina Pavludi (EMBRC) B Reference libraries, Bioinformatics, Taxonomies (data) Emilie Boulanger and Saara Suominen (UNESCO) C Biobanks, Culture collections, Taxonomies (concepts) Pascal Hablutzel (VLIZ) and Tom Collart (Seascope Belgium) Attendees can return to the previous group or select a new one Attendees can take breaks as and when they wish during the session
17:00 - 17:30	Plenary: summary of the breakouts. Workshop debrief and next steps

Breakout group A: *DNA and biodiversity data publishers*

Day 2. 14:30-15:45 16:15-17:30

14:00 -14:30	Plenary: summary and intro to the sessions
14:30 - 15:30	Miro board work. Getting your feedback on specific points in the Landscaping report. Pre-workshop reading material can be found in the public folder for the workshop (https://tinyurl.com/56rxpccj), specifically in “README” and “Day 2: landscaping recommendations and discussion points”. Coffee/health break can be freely taken during this session.
15:30 - 16:00	Plenary: summary of the breakouts / Break
16:00 - 17:00	Continuation of Miro board work. Continuation of the first session
17:00 - 17:30	Plenary: summary of the breakouts. Workshop debrief and next steps

Breakout group B: *Reference libraries, Bioinformatics, Taxonomies (data)*

Day 2. 14:30-15:45 16:15-17:30

14:00 -14:30	Plenary: summary and intro to the sessions
14:30 - 15:30	Miro board work. Getting your feedback on specific points in the Landscaping report. Pre-workshop reading material can be found in the public folder for the workshop (https://tinyurl.com/56rxpccj), specifically in “README” and “Day 2: landscaping recommendations and discussion points”. Coffee/health break can be freely taken during this session.
15:30 - 16:00	Plenary: summary of the breakouts / Break
16:00 - 17:00	Continuation of Miro board work. Continuation of the first session
17:00 - 17:30	Plenary: summary of the breakouts. Workshop debrief and next steps

Breakout group C: *Biobanks, Culture collections, Taxonomies (concepts)*

Day 2. 14:30-15:45 16:15-17:30

14:00 -14:30	Plenary: summary and intro to the sessions
14:30 - 15:30	Miro board-led discussion. Pre-workshop reading material can be found in the public folder for the workshop (https://tinyurl.com/56rxpccj), specifically in “README” and “Day 2: landscaping recommendations and discussion points”.
15:30 - 16:00	Plenary: summary of the breakouts / Break
16:00 - 17:00	Miro board-led discussion. Continuation of the first session
17:00 - 17:30	Plenary: summary of the breakouts. Workshop debrief and next steps